

SEMANTIC-GRAMMATIC CHARACTERISTICS OF ENGLISH
PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS RELATED TO LABOR AND PROFESSIONAL
ACTIVITY.

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Abstract: This thesis analyzes the semantic, grammatical, and emotional-expressive properties of professional phraseological units. The holistic meaning of phraseological units, their nominative and communicative types, and grammatical changes (verb tenses and voice category) are illustrated on the basis of examples. The role of these units in increasing the imagery and expressiveness of speech is also shown.

Key words: phraseological units, phraseological meaning, semantic structure, grammatical structure, nominative phraseologisms, communicative phraseologisms, passive voice, active voice.

Introduction:

Phraseological units are one of the important layers of language, embodying the thinking, culture and lifestyle of the people. In particular, professional phraseological units are of particular importance as they reflect a person's work activity, professional experience, and also social attitude. In this thesis, the semantic-grammatical structure of phraseologisms with a professional component and their emotional-expressive properties were analyzed based on examples.

Phraseological units are language units consisting of at least two or more words, semantically integral and ready to be used in speech. They consist of phraseological meaning and additional connotations.

Main body:

Phraseological meaning is the general and integral meaning expressed by phraseological units, which differs from the lexical meaning of individual components. Cognitive linguistics expert Evens defined phraseological meaning as follows: "a semantic structure that is entrenched and integrally stored in linguistic memory, and is formed as a result of transfer between concepts"[1]. Mona Baker, analyzing phraseological units from the perspective of translation and semantics, described them as units of a strictly defined grammatical and lexical form, the meaning of which does not depend on the meaning of its components[2]. In her opinion, phraseological meaning should embody stability

and semantic integrity. For example, the phrase: too many cooks spoil the broth, when translated literally, means that if there are too many cooks, the soup will be spoiled, but the meaning of this phrase is that if too many people interfere, the result will be bad. Also, the phrase "every cook praises his own broth" means that everyone praises their own work. Several similar examples can be seen below:

A hard nut to crack- very difficult issue

Go to extra mile- make extra effort

Work one's finger to the bone- work very hard

Meet a deadline- to complete within the specified time

The meanings of "difficulty" and "obligation" are expressed in an intensified manner in these expressions. The main characteristics of phraseological meanings are integrity, complexity, breadth, and mobility. Therefore, phraseological meaning is broader and more complex than lexical meaning.

Profession-related phraseological units are semantically divided into nominative and communicative types. Nominative phraseologisms name an object, action, or sign. For example, expressions such as *learn the ropes* (to learn the secrets of work), *get down to business* (to start business) directly express work activities, while expressions such as *run the show* (to manage work), *be at the helm* (to lead) indicate leadership and management processes.

Communicative phraseological units express an idea. Also, most of them are mainly in the form of proverbs. For example, let's take the expression *a bad workman blames his tools*. It means that a bad workman blames his tools. Another example is the expression *jack of all trades, master of none*, which means that he knows everything, but is not a master at anything.

Phraseological units are composed of at least two independent words in terms of expression, and although they can be syntactically in the form of a compound or a sentence, they are semantically considered a coherent unit.

1. **Idiomatic phrases:** *to burn the candle at both ends*- to work excessively;

To cut corners- to sacrifice quality or to bend the rules to make;

A steep learning curve- a complex process that requires a lot of learning in a short time.

To be in the loop- to be aware of the development of events/ to be within the scope of information.

2. **Idiomatic sentences:** *the ball is in your court*- it is your turn/ it's your turn to make a decision;

Do not burn your bridges- do not close the doors;

That is the way the cookie crumbles-it is fate/ things are the way they are (accepting a bad situation);

We will cross that bridge when we come to it- we will solve the problem when it is comes (not worry ahead of time).

One of the unique features of phraseological units is their figurativeness and emotional-expressiveness. For example, the expression to *burn the midnight oil* figuratively expresses the meaning of working at night. *Pull a fast one* is used in the sense of cheating, while the expression *cut corners* expresses the negative meaning of doing work in a low-quality, easy way.

It is possible to observe the use of verbs in phraseological units in different tenses and their adaptation to the person. These changes affect the grammatical form of the expression, but do not change its main meaning. Examples of this can be seen in the following sentences:

Roll up your sleeves- *get to work seriously.*

He rolls up his sleeves- he gets to work seriously;

*He rolled up his sleeves yesterday -*he got to work seriously yesterday;

Get down to business- *to start work.*

Let's get down to business- let's get started;

They got down to business quickly- they started working quickly;

Phraseological units can also change from active to passive voice during use. Although this change affects the structure of the sentence, the general meaning of the expression remains unchanged or there is a slight stylistic change. For instance:

They called the shots- *the shots were called by them*

Cook the books- *the books were cooked*

Pull a fast one- *a fast one was pulled*

Not all phraseological units can be changed to passive voice. Some phraseological units are used only in the active voice. For example, if we take the expression *reap what you saw*, it is often used in the active voice, or the expression *learn the ropes* is rarely used in the passive voice, since it is artificially pronounced in this voice. Therefore, the possibility of changing the voice in phraseological units depends on their use and structure.

Phraseological units related to professions are related to various fields. For example: *the cobbler should stick to his last* is related to crafts and means that everyone should do their job. The construction-related phrase "*build castles in the air*" means to make plans that will not come true. The agricultural phrase "*reap what you saw*" embodies the real -life truth that you reap what you sow. Also,

"*make hay while the sun shines*" is used in the sense of taking advantage of the opportunity in time.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, professional phraseological units are semantically complex, grammatically diverse, and emotionally-expressively rich language units. With their help, a person's work activity, professional experience, and place in society are figuratively expressed. Therefore, such phraseologisms are an important tool for enriching the language and making it more expressive, as well as increasing its naturalness.

References

1. Evans V. Cognitive linguistics: An introduction / V. Evans, M. Green. – Edinburgh : Edinburgh University Press, 2006.
2. Baker M. In other words: A coursebook on translation / M. Baker. – 3rd ed. – London ; New York : Routledge, 2018.
3. Rakhmatullayev Sh. Phraseological dictionary of the Uzbek language– Tashkent : O'qituvchi, 1992.
4. Kunin A. V. Course of modern English language (phraseology) – Moscow, 1986.
5. Bafoyeva M. The use of phraseological synonyms in literary speech / M. Bafoyeva. – Tashkent, 2003.
6. Kizi, S. B. Y. (2022). Linguo-cultural characteristics of speech etiquette occurring in discourse. *Current Research Journal of Philological Sciences*, 3(11), 59-63.
7. Dilnoza, A., & Shakhnoza, B. (2024). Interactive language learning strategies for enhancing vocabulary acquisition. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 4(7S), 62-66.
8. Bobojonova, S. (2022). Pragmatic interpretation of educational discourse and expression of dialogic discourse in the communication process.

